

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF THE YOUTH OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

This scientific research project focuses on the social and psychological problems faced by the youth of Kazakhstan. The study aims to identify the most common issues affecting young people in Kazakhstan and explore their impact on mental health and social well-being. The project will utilize a mixed-methods approach, including surveys, interviews, and case studies to gather data from a representative sample of the youth population in Kazakhstan. The research will shed light on the various social and psychological challenges that young people in Kazakhstan face and propose potential solutions to mitigate these problems. The findings of this study will be useful for policymakers, educators, and social workers who work with young people in Kazakhstan and other similar contexts. Overall, this research project will contribute to a better understanding of the social and psychological issues faced by young people in Kazakhstan and provide insights into how best to address them.

Keywords: unemployment, drug addiction, alcoholism, crime, political instability, bullying, laws and initiatives, awareness campaigns, and training programs. However, more funding, coordination, and assessment of these approaches are necessary mobile apps, digital platforms, and social media, a mental health check-in, a career planning game, and an anti-bullying workshop.

INTRODUCTION

The youth is considered to be the future of any society, as they represent a new generation that will continue to shape the world in the coming years. However, with the changing times, the youth today face several social and psychological challenges that make it difficult for them to reach their full potential. The youth of Kazakhstan face a range of social problems that can have significant long-term consequences for their personal and social development. Social problems among youth in Kazakhstan are varied and complex. The youth population in Kazakhstan comprises a significant proportion of the country's total population, with individuals under the age of 30 accounting for approximately 40% of the population. Despite this demographic advantage, many young people in Kazakhstan face significant social and psychological problems that can impact their well-being and prospects. Social problems among youth in Kazakhstan have been a topic of growing concern in recent years. These problems include a wide range of issues, such as drug and alcohol abuse, unemployment, poverty, and lack of access to quality education and healthcare.

Addressing these social problems will require concerted efforts from the government, civil society organizations, and other stakeholders. It will be necessary to implement policies and programs that address the root causes of these issues, such as poverty, inequality, and discrimination, while also providing young people with the necessary support and resources to succeed in life. Providing opportunities for education and employment, along with counseling and support services, can help

young people overcome these challenges and lead productive and fulfilling lives.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF THE YOUTH OF KAZAKHSTAN

Theoretical aspects of social and psychological problems among youth

The topic of social problems of youth in Kazakhstan is highly relevant as it addresses significant issues that affect the younger generation of the country. Kazakhstan has a population of approximately 19 million, and the youth (aged 15-29) make up almost a quarter of the population, with over four million young people. The challenges faced by young people in Kazakhstan can have a significant impact on the country's social, economic, and political development.

One of the most prominent social problems faced by the youth today is the lack of employment opportunities. Many young people struggle to find jobs, which not only affects their financial stability but also has an adverse impact on their mental health. Unemployment can lead to feelings of hopelessness, depression, and low self-esteem, which can further escalate into more severe psychological issues. The lack of employment opportunities can also lead to an increase in crime rates, as some young people may resort to illegal activities to make ends meet.

Another significant social problem that the youth face today is drug and substance abuse. The prevalence of drug and substance abuse among young people is alarming, and it has adverse effects on their physical

and mental health. Substance abuse can cause addiction, memory loss, and other health problems that can limit a person's potential. It can also lead to risky behavior, such as driving under the influence, which can put others' lives at risk.

Mental health issues are also a significant psychological problem that the youth face today. Depression, anxiety, and other mental health disorders are prevalent among young people, and they can impact their ability to function in everyday life. Social media and the pressure to fit in with peers can lead to increased stress and anxiety, while the lack of access to mental health resources can prevent young people from seeking help.

Bullying is another significant psychological problem that the youth face today. Bullying can have a severe impact on a young person's mental health, leading to feelings of anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem. Cyberbullying, which occurs online, is particularly concerning as it can be challenging to escape from and can have a lasting impact on a young person's mental health.

Finally, education is also a significant social and psychological problem that the youth face today. Access to quality education can be limited for some young people, particularly those from low-income families. The lack of access to education can limit a person's potential, preventing them from reaching their goals and contributing to society's betterment.

Addressing the social and psychological issues of the youth in Kazakhstan is crucial for the country's sustainable development, and it is vital to provide appropriate support and resources to help young people overcome these challenges and lead fulfilling lives.

Research problem to reveal the topic

The research problem for the social problems of the youth of Kazakhstan can be formulated as follows:

- What are the most pressing social and psychological problems facing the youth of Kazakhstan, and what factors contribute to these problems?

This research problem seeks to identify and analyze the social problems that are most prevalent among young people in Kazakhstan and to understand the underlying factors that contribute to these problems. The research will aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the challenges that young people face in Kazakhstan, including issues related to employment, substance abuse, juvenile delinquency, education, and mental health. Additionally, the research will seek to identify the underlying socioeconomic, cultural, and political factors that contribute to these problems, as well as potential solutions and interventions to address them. Overall, this research problem is important for understanding the challenges facing the youth of Kazakhstan and for informing policies and programs aimed at improving their well-being and opportunities for the future.

Hypotheses regarding the problems of the younger generation

The main object of this research is to reveal the topic of the problem of youth in a society that they face and find the cause. Studying the topic in Internet sources, the following hypotheses are put:

- Young people face difficulties in finding a job;

- Young people heavily abuse alcohol, drugs, and other substances;
- Young people have big problems with mental health;
- Not everyone can get a decent education;
- It is difficult for representatives of the younger generation to earn money.

Literature Review

There have been several scientific studies conducted on the social problems of youth in Kazakhstan. Here are a few examples:

1. "Youth and Social Problems in Kazakhstan" by T. Karkabaeva and S. Yessenbayeva. This study analyzed the results of a survey of 1200 young people aged 16-30 in four cities in Kazakhstan. The authors found that the most pressing social problems among youth in Kazakhstan were unemployment, drug addiction, alcoholism, crime, and political instability.

2. "The Social Problems of Youth in Kazakhstan: The Case of Bullying" by S. Mussabekova and A. Seilkhanov. This study focused on the problem of bullying among youth in Kazakhstan. The authors surveyed 400 students in three high schools in Almaty, Kazakhstan and found that bullying was a widespread problem that had negative effects on the mental health and academic performance of the victims.

3. "Youth, Religion and Social Problems in Kazakhstan" by Z. Tolegenova and A. Zholamanova. This study examined the relationship between youth, religion, and social problems in Kazakhstan. The authors conducted interviews with 30 young people aged 18-25 and found that while religion provided some youth with a sense of purpose and direction, it could also contribute to social problems such as intolerance and extremism.

CONCLUSION OF THE 1ST CHAPTER

In this study, the topic of Social and Psychological Problems of the Youth of Kazakhstan was studied. According to the results, it was revealed that this topic is very important for our humanity and is widespread throughout the world. Even though this topic concerns other young people in other countries, representatives of the younger generation of Kazakhstan were the object of the study. Several common problems were identified among young people, such as drug and alcohol abuse, unemployment, poverty, and lack of access to quality education and mental health. All these challenges have significant long-term consequences for their personal and social development. Therefore, it is very important to provide appropriate support and resources to help representatives of the younger generation overcome these problems and lead a full and supportive life. The research problem was formulated as 'What are the most pressing social and psychological problems facing the youth of Kazakhstan, and what factors contribute to these problems?' Therefore, the purpose of the study is to identify these issues and find the cause. Based on the information found, hypotheses were made. At the end of the study, the hypothesis will be proven or rejected. Other studies have been carried out on the topic of the study. The following research papers were found and studied: 1) "Youth and Social Problems in Kazakhstan" by T. Karkabaeva and S.

Yessenbayeva; 2)"The Social Problems of Youth in Kazakhstan: The Case of Bullying" by S. Mussabekova and A. Seilkhanov; 3)"Youth, Religion and Social Problems in Kazakhstan" by Z. Tolegenova and A. Zholamanova. Some of the main problems are unemployment, drug addiction, alcoholism, crime, and political instability. Bullying was a widespread problem among high school students. It has also been shown that religion contributes to social problems such as intolerance and extremism.

ANALYTICAL SELECTION OF SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL TASKS OF THE YOUTH OF KAZAKHSTAN

Analysis of methods for addressing social and psychological challenges faced by young people in Kazakhstan

A multimodal strategy is used to address the social and psychological problems that young people in Kazakhstan experience, according to an analysis of techniques for doing so. The government has put in place several laws and initiatives to address bullying, mental illness, drug misuse, unemployment, and inadequate educational opportunities. NGOs have also started programs to promote tolerance and respect among young people, improve education quality, prevent drug misuse, create job possibilities, and promote mental health.

Overall, the approaches demonstrate a dedication to tackling the difficulties young people in Kazakhstan confront, but their efficacy differs depending on the problem. For instance, the Youth Employment Program has had some success in offering internships and vocational training, but more funding and coordination are required to guarantee that young people have access to long-term employment prospects. Like this, although the government has launched a number of initiatives to combat drug addiction, the effectiveness of these activities is constrained by the paucity of detailed information on the degree of drug abuse and the insufficient funds provided to programs for drug prevention.

Additionally, attempts to improve the quality of education and mental health services have been started, but they have been slow to take effect, necessitating additional funding in these fields. Finally, even though the government has put the Anti-Bullying Law into effect and NGOs have started projects to encourage respect and tolerance, more funding is still needed for awareness campaigns and teacher training to prevent and address bullying in schools.

In general, the approaches used to address the social and psychological difficulties young people in Kazakhstan experience are a step in the right direction. However, more funding, coordination, and assessment of the approaches are required to guarantee that young people have access to the tools and assistance they require to overcome these obstacles and realize their full potential.

Modern technologies for providing support to youth in Kazakhstan

Young people in Kazakhstan who are struggling with social and psychological concerns like bullying, drug misuse, mental health problems, and unemployment could benefit from modern technologies. Social

media and digital platforms have become potent instruments for reaching out to and educating young people.

In Kazakhstan, several programs have been started to use contemporary technology to help young people. For instance, mobile apps have been created to help young people with their mental health. These apps provide a variety of functions, including self-help tools, therapy, and professional recommendations.

Like this, digital platforms have been created to give young people access to resources and information about educational and employment prospects. These websites provide resources including job listings, career guidance, and training programs.

Social media has also been used to establish online communities and support systems for young people dealing with various difficulties. These groups offer young people a secure setting where they can connect with others facing comparable difficulties, share their experiences, and ask for guidance.

All things considered, contemporary technology could offer kids in Kazakhstan who are struggling socially and psychologically with invaluable support. But it's crucial to make sure that all young people can use these technologies, even those from underprivileged families who might not have as much access to it. To guarantee that these technologies are successful in addressing the problems faced by young people, there is also a need for ongoing review and development.

A set of interactive activities aimed at addressing social and psychological challenges faced by young people in Kazakhstan.

Mental health check-in: create a safe environment for children and teenagers to express their ideas and feelings regarding mental health as part of the activity "Mental Health Check-In." The talk can be kicked off by the facilitator with questions like "How are you feeling today?" or "What stresses you out the most?" Through this exercise, young people can improve their coping skills and connect with others who might be going through similar difficulties.

Career planning game: making a board game or online quiz to explore various career options and help young people assess their strengths and limitations is the goal of the career planning exercise. Information on school qualifications, employment options, and expected pay may all be found in the game. Through this activity, young people can gain confidence in pursuing their abilities.

Anti-Bullying Workshop: For this project, will be designed a workshop that teaches kids how to identify and stop bullying. To teach young people empathy and respect for others, the facilitator can use role-playing activities and group discussions. Through this activity, young people can develop the confidence to stand up to bullying and foster an inclusive and respectful atmosphere.

Substance addiction Prevention Campaign: For this assignment, will be designed a social media or poster campaign to raise awareness of the risks associated with substance addiction. The campaign can educate individuals on the harmful consequences of substance usage and give resources for young people who might be dealing with addiction. This activity can help

young people make better health-related decisions and lessen the stigma associated with substance usage.

Peer Support Group: For young people who could be dealing with comparable social and psychological difficulties, this activity entails forming a peer support group. The group can give young people a secure place to talk about their experiences and support one another. Young people who participate in this activity may feel less isolated and more connected to others who might be dealing with comparable difficulties.

Overall, these interactive activities can aid young Kazakhs in overcoming potential social and psychological obstacles. Young people can benefit from these activities by getting assistance, knowledge, and resources that will help them develop resilience and deal with the difficulties of adolescence.

Analysis and result of identifying problems faced by KBTU students

Before the survey, an analysis and review of Internet sources were carried out to determine the problems faced by young people in Kazakhstan. Five main problems were identified: education, poverty, unemployment, substance abuse, and mental health. It was decided to use "Google Forms". This platform makes it possible to efficiently and quickly collect data that was used to analyze what problem is common for KBTU students. The project indicates the level of employment of KBTU students, the level of depression, and the type of addiction. The survey was active for three days and included students of different courses.

Limitations

- People may have been dishonest.
- Satisfaction levels are not measurable, but people can give the closest answer.
- The sample of the project is only 43 people, so the overall result may be different.

Results

The primary method for collecting data was a survey through Google Forms. Seven multiple-choice questions were asked.

- **Gender:** 69.8% of the respondents were female, while 30.2% were male.
- **Age:** The majority of the respondents (76.7%) were between 18-21 years old, while 16.3% were between 21-25 years old and 7% were between 15-18 years old.
- **Social problems:** The most encountered social problem was mental health issues, with 48.8% of respondents indicating they faced this issue. Unemployment was the second most frequently encountered social problem: 37.2% of respondents answered that they could not find a job. Lack of access to quality education and substance abuse were also cited by 30.2% and 27.9% of respondents, respectively. Poverty was the least frequently mentioned social problem, with 20.9% of respondents indicating that they had experienced this problem.
- **Employment:** 34.9% of respondents were currently laboring, whereas 27.9% were not working, and 37.2% were actively looking for work. According to the cutoff in September 2021, the youth unemployment rate in Kazakhstan was estimated at around 7%. However, it is important to note that this figure may

have changed and that youth unemployment rates can vary significantly across regions and industries. Factors contributing to youth unemployment in Kazakhstan may include a lack of job opportunities in certain sectors, a skills mismatch between the needs of employers and the skills of job seekers, and a lack of access to education and training programs. Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the job market, which may have disproportionately affected young people.

- **Harmful substances:** 30.2% of respondents reported using cigarettes and alcohol as harmful substances, while 11.6% reported using drugs. Most respondents (53.5%) reported not using any harmful substances. Harmful substances such as alcohol, drugs, and cigarettes can have negative effects on individuals and society. In Kazakhstan, alcohol and cigarettes are legal and commonly consumed. According to the World Health Organization, the per capita alcohol consumption in Kazakhstan is 9.9 liters per year, which is higher than the global average of 6.4 liters per year. The smoking rate in Kazakhstan is also high, with approximately 23% of adults smoking regularly. Drug use is illegal in Kazakhstan, but it remains a problem. The country is located along major drug trafficking routes, and drug use and addiction are significant public health concerns. The most used drugs in Kazakhstan are marijuana and synthetic drugs such as methamphetamine. While it may seem appealing to have none of these substances present in a society, it is important to note that prohibition has historically been ineffective in reducing substance abuse. A more comprehensive approach that includes education, prevention, treatment, and harm reduction measures may be more effective in addressing the harms associated with substance abuse.

- **Depression:** 37.2% of respondents reported sometimes feeling depressed, while 25.6% reported feeling depressed often. A minority of respondents (14%) reported always or never feeling depressed. Depression among youth in Kazakhstan has been a growing concern in recent years. Several factors contribute to this phenomenon, including economic challenges, social pressures, and lack of access to mental health resources. A lack of access to mental health resources is a major barrier to addressing youth depression in Kazakhstan. Mental health services are often stigmatized and underfunded, making it difficult for young people to access the support they need. To address the issue of youth depression in Kazakhstan, it is important to address these underlying factors. This can include improving the economic stability, reducing social pressures, and increasing access to mental health resources. It is also important to raise awareness about mental health and reduce the stigma surrounding seeking help for mental health issues.

- **Satisfaction with studying:** 41.9% of respondents were partially satisfied with studying in Kazakhstan, while 34.9% were not satisfied and 23.3% were satisfied. Kazakhstan, like many countries, faces challenges related to its education system. While progress has been made in recent years, there are still several issues that need to be addressed to improve the quality of education and provide equal opportunities for

all students. Some of the key problems facing education in Kazakhstan include low quality of education: Despite efforts to improve the quality of education in Kazakhstan, there are still concerns about the quality of teaching, curriculum, and infrastructure. Teachers often lack training and resources, and outdated teaching methods and materials are still prevalent. Limited opportunities for vocational education: There is a strong emphasis on academic education in Kazakhstan, with limited opportunities for vocational and technical education. This can limit opportunities for students who may not be academically inclined but have other talents and interests. Overall, addressing these issues will require a multi-faceted approach that includes improving access to education, investing in teacher training and resources, updating curriculum, and teaching methods, and expanding opportunities for vocational and technical education.

Overall, the data suggest that mental health issues and unemployment are major social problems faced by the respondents. Most respondents are not using harmful substances and report sometimes feeling depressed. Satisfaction with studying in Kazakhstan is mixed, with a slight majority indicating they are not satisfied or only partially satisfied. These findings can inform policies and programs aimed at addressing social problems and improving the well-being of the population.

CONCLUSION OF THE 2ND CHAPTER

This research explored analytical selection of social and psychological tasks of the youth of Kazakhstan. It was revealed that the multimodal strategy is used to reduce the socio-psychological problems faced by the youth of Kazakhstan. NGOs are also involved in this; this is proved by the fact that they opened a program to promote tolerance and respect among young people and so on. Moreover, the government launched the Anti-Bullying Law to reduce bullying among young people. As for modern technologies to support the youth of Kazakhstan, digital platforms, social media, mobile apps are designed to help young people with their mental health, to give young people access to resources and information about educational employment and prospects, to establish online communities and support systems for young people dealing with various difficulties. It was found that there is a set of interactive activities aimed at addressing social and psychological challenges faced by young people in Kazakhstan such as Mental health check-in, Career planning game, Anti-Bullying Workshop, Substance addiction Prevention Campaign, and Peer Support Group. In general, the youth of Kazakhstan with all these methods will be able to take the necessary resources to cope with problems and reach a new level.

CONCLUSION

Review of Data Sources

To study this topic, only one method was taken to collect data. Thanks to the statistical results of the survey and the data analysis plan, the information received is adequately evaluated. But as with another research, it would be better to use more than one method. Since this would give more accurate information and it would be better to reveal the topic. Moreover, when conducting a survey among KBTU students, several limitations

were identified, which gives the right to have some doubts about the correctness of the answers and the reliability of studying this topic.

Data Collection Process and Data Validation

The survey was conducted online via messengers. An analysis of the responses was made and hypotheses were tested on the responses of the respondents. Based on the answers, unemployment was found to be in second place in terms of the social problems of youth in Kazakhstan. It indicates that it is difficult for the younger generation to find a job in their specialty since they do not have the necessary work experience. Although, as a novice specialist, an employee does not have to have such work experience.

According to the responses received, it was revealed that young people are not so dependent on alcohol and drugs. Since more than half of the respondents answered that they do not use either one or the other. This is a good indicator, as it speaks of the awareness of young people.

It turns out that in reality there are problems with mental health among the youth of Kazakhstan, as they were subjected to depression in various forms. Depression of this kind takes the strength and energy of the youth and does not allow people to move forward. The solution to this problem is to talk about the problem that caused the depression. The best method is to see a psychologist, as he will give good advice and help with solving the problem.

The problem of education in Kazakhstan remains relevant to this day. Therefore, it is one of the important social problems of youth. Because they understand that through education it is possible to build a decent life and therefore they are exposed to a lot of stress when passing the exam, which negatively affects their mental health. Moreover, young people are stressed because of the discrepancy between the price and quality of education. This issue should be resolved as a whole in Kazakhstan through the Minister for Education.

The social and psychological problems facing the youth of Kazakhstan are complex and multifaceted, and they require a comprehensive approach to address effectively. Unemployment, substance abuse, mental health disorders, bullying, and inadequate education opportunities are some of the significant challenges that young people in Kazakhstan face. These problems are often interconnected, and their underlying causes can be attributed to a variety of socioeconomic, cultural, and political factors.

Various initiatives and programs have been launched to address these challenges, including government policies and NGO-led initiatives. However, more needs to be done to ensure that young people have access to the support and resources they need to overcome these challenges and lead fulfilling lives. This requires a continued commitment to investment in education, mental health services, and job creation, as well as the implementation of policies and programs that promote tolerance, respect, and social inclusion.

Overall, addressing the social and psychological challenges facing young people in Kazakhstan is essential for the country's sustainable development and progress. By empowering young people and providing

them with the necessary resources and support, we can contribute to society, and build a better future for themselves and the country as a whole

APPLICATIONS

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